

EVALUATION OF TECHNOLOGY-DEPENDENT MAXIMUM POWER POINT CURRENT AND VOLTAGE DEGRADATION IN A TEMPERATE CLIMATE

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ABSTRACT: In this paper the maximum power point current and voltage degradation of eight different photovoltaic technologies (27 systems) installed in a temperate climate is studied. The plant was installed in 2010 and seven years of production are considered. A performance loss over time has been observed for all systems. Most systems show a stronger relative decrease in current compared to voltage. The connection between performance losses broken down into these two parameters can lead to findings of which degradation modes appear in the PV system. Depending on the predominant performance loss parameter, specific degradation modes were suspected and several PV plant inspections, including IV curve measurements and electroluminescence as well as infrared imagery, took place to confirm these hypotheses. Degradation in current was detected in all systems and can be connected to hot cells, fractured cells, soiling as well as other root causes. A decrease in voltage was not observed for crystalline systems but is severe for copper indium (gallium) selenide as well as amorphous silicon systems and is suspected to be caused by a reduction in the conductivity of the metal contacts and a decreasing ability of the photovoltaic active material to separate the charge carriers. The outcomes of this study might contribute to O&M related improvements of failure detection.

Keywords: PV system, performance degradation, system performance

1 INTRODUCTION

Photovoltaic devices convert the energy of the sun directly into electricity. This technology became widely available in the late 1990's and evolved from being a niche product to a widely accepted energy source and business investment. To ensure a safe, reliable and profitable operation of PV systems, possible risks during operation need to be minimized and performance reducing effects fast detected in order to be eliminated. The project "Solar Bankability" was created to contribute to the reduction of investment risks in photovoltaic projects [1]. Further research in this direction is crucial and will eventually contribute to a further increase of confidence in photovoltaics as a mature energy source.

PV systems are subject to continuous cycles of temperature, humidity, irradiation, mechanical stress and soiling. These stresses lead to the occurrence of degradation modes (DM). DM are effects that reduce the output power of a PV system irreversibly and might create safety problems [2]. Each mode has other causes and is triggered differently. It develops either in isolation or in combination with other DM or technical risks and might lead to the failure of a PV module. The term failure is for electrotechnical devices defined as "the termination of the ability of an item to perform a required function" [3].

An important part plays the detection of DM and other performance decreasing occurrences through operation & maintenance (O&M) routines. The ideal case would be to detect DM and other technical risks early and reliable with minimal effort.

On one hand O&M companies perform field inspections where, among other things, IV-curves are recorded or electroluminescence images taken, to detect DM or other performance impairing technical risks. On the other side system degradation is discovered by studying performance rating parameters of a PV system, for example the maximum power or the performance ratio (PR), and calculating the performance loss (PL). Although a great amount of publications focuses on degradation and improvement of degradation models, a deeper understanding of the current and voltage behavior of a PV

system could lead to the connection of the aforementioned operations. The correlations between the maximum power point current (I_{MPP}) and irradiation as well as the maximum power point voltage (V_{MPP}) and temperature are indicators, which might contribute to the understanding of a decrease in a PV systems performance. A better understanding of the time dependent behavior of I_{MPP} and V_{MPP} values, which are available from most data-loggers of installed PV systems, might enhance the knowledge of what is happening in the PV module over time. Especially in regards to solar cell parameters, like short-circuit current density, open-circuit voltage, fill factor, series resistance or shunt resistance, this is a promising approach to find root causes for degradation.

This paper presents a study of the time evolution of I_{MPP} and V_{MPP} values of eight different PV module technologies (27 PV systems) installed in a temperate climate for seven years. Each PV system consists of one or two strings. The idea of the investigation is to find dependencies between certain DM/technical failures and patterns in the time series. Therefore, next to the statistical degradation studies, field visits were conducted including IV-curve measurements, visual inspections and capturing electroluminescence (EL) as well as infrared (IR) images.

2 METHODOLOGY

2.1 PV system

The PV installation in question consists of 27 different PV systems of varying size, which cover eight different technologies and have an overall nominal power of 59kW. The test facility is located at the Airport Bolzano Dolomiti in South Tyrol/Italy and installed at a fixed tilt of 30° and an orientation of 8.5° west of south. The prevailing climate is according to Köppen classified as Cfb (temperate, without dry season, warm summer). In close proximity to the test side, a dedicated meteo-station is operated. Here, the direct normal and diffuse horizontal irradiance as well as the global plane-of-array (POA) irradiance, the wind speed and the ambient temperature is measured with a measurement frequency of 1 min. The electrical parameter

of the inverter have a resolution of 15 min and because of that, the weather data are averaged on a 15 min interval. The technologies installed are micromorphous silicon (μ morph), amorphous silicon (a-Si), cadmium telluride (CdTe), copper indium (gallium) selenide (CIGS), silicon solar cells made out of a heterojunction with an intrinsic thin layer (HIT), monocrystalline silicon (mc-Si), polycrystalline silicon (pc-Si) and polycrystalline silicon string ribbon (ribbon). Three different kind of a-Si systems are considered, namely with single, double and triple junctions.

2.2 Data preparation

Before any calculation is performed, the data are subject to certain filters, correction and normalization. First, all 15-min data, which have a POA irradiance lower than 500W/m^2 and higher than 1200W/m^2 are excluded. At a later stage, the temperature coefficients from the PV module datasheets are used to perform temperature corrections. These temperature coefficients, obtained for V_{OC} and I_{SC} , are retrieved at a POA irradiance (G_{POA}) of 1000W/m^2 . This filter is a compromise of excluding not too many data and reducing the uncertainty of applying the coefficients. A second filter concerns the performance ratio. The PR is calculated by dividing the final (array) yield $Y_{f(a)}$ (depending if AC- or DC-power is evaluated) with the reference yield Y_{ref} [4]. The yields are ratios of measured values of power/irradiance and nominal values.

$$PR = \frac{Y_f}{Y_{ref}} = \frac{P_{AC}/P_{nom}}{G_{POA}/G_{STC}}, \quad PR_{DC} = \frac{Y_a}{Y_{ref}} = \frac{P_{DC}/P_{nom}}{G_{POA}/G_{STC}}$$

Here, P_{nom} is the nominal power of the PV system and G_{STC} is the irradiance at Standard Test Conditions (STC with cell temperature T_{STC} of 25°C , irradiance G_{STC} of 1000W/m^2 and air mass of 1.5). When studying the PV performance, it is advisable to use DC related performance metrics in order to eliminate eventual influences due to inverter degradation.

The filter excludes all data points whose 15-min PR value is not within a $\pm 2\sigma$ -interval of its most likely value (PR_{mode}) within the month. Like this, data corresponding to inhomogeneous irradiance conditions between the weather station and the PV system are eliminated [5]. Approximately 50% of the data (excluding nights) are filtered out.

In a next step, measured values for MPP current and voltage, I_{meas} and V_{meas} , are corrected to lower seasonality. Both parameter are corrected for temperature. Furthermore, I_{meas} is additionally corrected for irradiance because of its strong irradiance dependency. The following formulas are used:

$$V_{T_{corr}} = V_{meas} * \frac{1}{[1 + \beta * (T_{cell} - T_{STC})]}$$

$$I_{G,T_{corr}} = I_{meas} * \frac{G_{STC}}{G_{POA}} * \frac{1}{[1 + \alpha * (T_{cell} - T_{STC})]}$$

where β is the temperature coefficient in voltage [%/K], α the temperature coefficient in current [%/K] and T_{cell} is the cell temperature, which is calculated by [6]:

$$T_{cell} = T_{amb} + (NOCT - T_{NOCT}) * \frac{G_{POA}}{G_{NOCT}}$$

$NOCT$ is the Nominal Operating Cell Temperature from the datasheet and is determined under the following conditions: $T_{NOCT} = 20^\circ\text{C}$, $G_{NOCT} = 800\text{W/m}^2$ and a wind speed of 1m/s . Although measured cell temperatures are

available, it was decided to use the modelled values because the measured data are incomplete and some temperature sensors lost its connection to the backside of the PV modules for a certain period.

Afterwards, the corrected values are normalized according to [7] in order to achieve better comparability of the behavior among the systems.

$$V_{norm}[\%] = \frac{V_{T_{corr}}}{V_{STC} * n_{modules_{series}}}$$

$$I_{norm}[\%] = \frac{I_{G,T_{corr}}}{I_{STC} * n_{modules_{parallel}}}$$

Finally, the normalized current, voltage and performance ratio is aggregated to monthly values. This was done to remove strong data oscillation due to short term variations.

2.3 Calculation methods

In order to verify the degradation of the different systems, the yearly performance loss (PL) of normalized monthly current and voltage time series as well as PR values is calculated using the software R. Thereby, seasonal-trend decomposition using LOESS (STL) is applied on the prepared data [8], [9]. By using STL, the seasonality and a remainder are separated from a set of measured time series data to receive a clear trend over time, and it is described by:

$$Y_t = T_t + S_t + R_t$$

STL uses locally weighted regression and smoothing to filter out the trend. This statistical method was chosen in order to reduce the performance loss uncertainties by removing seasonal effects and noise from the time series. To receive the PL a simple linear regression of the trend line is performed. The parameter of the regression line are a , which is the gradient of the function, and b , which is the intercept with the y-axis. By applying the following formula:

$$PL = 12 * a$$

the yearly performance loss is calculated. Figure 1 shows I_{norm} of a pc-Si PV system together with its trend and the regression line of the trend.

Finally, the uncertainty of the PL is determined. Therefore, the confidence interval of the regression functions gradient is computed using a confidence level of 95%. The half width of the absolute interval value is multiplied by 12 (months per year).

Figure 1: Normalized & corrected monthly current values together with trend & regression line of pc-Si7 system

3 RESULTS

The following figures represent the yearly PL for I_{norm} , PR and V_{norm} , divided in crystalline and thin-film systems. For every PV system the PL values including uncertainties are shown. The horizontal red line indicates a yearly performance loss of 1%, which is a minimal performance guarantee many PV manufactures ensure for the first 10 years. When looking at Figure 2, it is visible that most crystalline systems operate within the guaranteed performance levels. For thin-film systems, more than the half experience a degradation of more than 1%/a.

Figure 2: Performance Loss [%/a] of I_{norm} (triangles), PR (circles) and V_{norm} (rhombi) of all crystalline PV systems

Figure 3: Performance Loss [%/a] of I_{norm} (triangles), PR (circles) and V_{norm} (rhombi) of all thin-film PV systems

For most systems under observation, the current degrades more strongly in comparison to the voltage, with loss rate values between 0.25% and 2% per year. The main drivers for this decrease in I_{norm} and a resulting reduced power output are a degradation in the short circuit current combined with a lowered fill factor due to a decreasing shunt resistance. This effect might be caused by soiling and occurring DM. The studied PV installation is not subject to periodical cleaning, and soiling in dry periods can have a noticeable impact. The most commonly reported DM occurring in crystalline systems installed in moderate climates are according to Jordan et al. [10] hot spots, potential induced degradation (PID) and circuitry discoloration (due to corrosion). Additionally, systems, which are in operation since more than 10 years, show frequently encapsulant discoloration, a DM with relatively low severity. In respect to thin-film systems, absorber corrosion and glass breakage seem to have a bigger impact [10, 11]. It has to be stressed that DM are rarely appearing isolated but often simultaneously, and interact with each other, since different modes are triggered by similar influences such as PV technology, climate or mounting type. Apart from the simultaneous appearance of DM the consideration of PV system performance, instead of single module performance, complicates the detection of specific

DM. Nevertheless, it was decided to study PV system degradation since system data, available from inverter, are more easily accessible and more relevant within the scope of this study and future applications.

Performance losses detected in crystalline silicon systems are exclusively due to a decreasing current. It is visible that monocrystalline (mc-Si) systems degrade less than polycrystalline (pc-Si) PV panels. Furthermore, pc-Si systems seem to show a wider distribution of performance loss rates than mc-Si. Pc-Si1 shows the highest degradation rate of all crystalline silicon systems in consideration, and is exceeding the maximum guaranteed performance loss stated on the datasheet (90% of initial power after 10 years). One reason can be traced back to two cells with considerably higher temperatures within the string, which were detected via infrared (IR) imagery. An IR image of one cell is shown in Figure 4. This effect might be caused by an accumulation and thermal recombination of charged carriers in the bad cells due to hot-spots or corroded/detached connections. The hotspots are having a visible impact on the IV curve of the system. Figure 5 shows the normalized measured IV curve at 872.3W/m^2 and 51.5°C cell temperature together with the computed initial curve at the measurement conditions and the initial curve at STC (using model according to De Soto et al. implemented in PVLIB [12, 13]). At low voltages the gradient of the curve is higher than in the initial state, which is assumed to be caused by cell mismatch and a reduced shunt resistance. This in turn creates alternate current pathways and ultimately contributes to the detected loss in I_{norm} . Another reason for the high loss in current might be the selected front-side glass of pc-Si1. The glass has a pyramid like pattern, visible in Figure 4, and it is expected to accumulate soiling “more efficiently”.

Figure 4: IR image of pc-Si1 system including hot cell, Front-side glass of pc-Si1

Figure 5: Normalized IV curve pc-Si1 system, red: measured curve, blue dashed: initial curve at measurement conditions, black dotted: initial curve at STC

A similar degradation pattern, although with higher current values, has been detected in the IV curves of pc-Si7 and mc-Si5. This pattern in turn can partly be traced back to fractured cells in some of the modules, visible in Figure 6 and Figure 7, where electroluminescence images of cells and modules are depicted.

Figure 6: EL image of module of pc-Si7

Figure 7: EL image of cells of mc-Si5

Circuitry discoloration was detected in several cells of the pc-Si2 system, which leads to a partial disconnection of the cells affected, connected to an associated shunt resistance loss. Figure 8 shows a cell, which has circuitry discoloration and cracks, possibly stemming from enlarging snail tracks, and an EL-image of the same cell, where a partial cell disconnection can be seen.

Figure 8: EL image and picture of pc-Si2 cell

Apart from the degradation modes shown, other minor degradation limiting effects were detected for crystalline systems, such as minor cell cracks or back-sheet cracking. The ribbon system can be affiliated to pc-Si systems due to their crystal structure and HIT to mc-Si systems. Their degradation behavior is similar to the one of these systems.

It became apparent that the detection of DM within thin-film systems is somewhat more complex. The lack of a crystalline structure and the low operating current makes the usage of EL imagery more difficult. Furthermore, the

apparent difference in performance loss behavior between crystalline and thin-film systems (visible in Figure 2 and Figure 3) leads to the conclusion, that different DM develop over time. Especially the CIGS and a-Si systems under observation behave differently. Here, higher performance losses in V_{norm} were observed. The highest overall losses of 2-3% per year in PR , partly due to a high degradation in V_{norm} , are recorded for CIGS 2, 3 and 4. The IV curve for CIGS3 is shown in Figure 9 (initial curves computed using model according to Vergura [14]). It can be seen that a decreasing voltage primarily triggers the overall performance loss. For this system, EL images were done, visible in Figure 10. In the initial state, the EL image looks normal but after field exposure some of the modules emit almost no light anymore. This was a very surprising discovery and until now it was not possible to connect it to a specific root cause.

Figure 9: Normalized IV curve CIGS3 system, red: measured curve, blue dashed: initial curve at measurement conditions, black dotted: initial curve at STC

Figure 10: EL image of CIGS3 module in initial state and after exposure in the field

Apart from the CIGS systems, 2j-a-Si1 shows a relatively high decrease in V_{norm} , but due to the low degradation in I_{norm} the overall performance loss is not as high as for the CIGS systems. Both single junction a-Si systems as well as the CdTe system show considerable performance losses, both in I_{norm} and V_{norm} , and a resulting PR of around 1.5%/a. A decrease in voltage is often related to an increasing series resistance, which might be connected to a decreasing conductivity of the metal contacts. Another root cause might be a chemical process within the active material, which affects the efficiency of the charge carrier separation. Micromorph silicon systems consist of a junction between amorphous silicon and microcrystalline silicon. Their temperature dependency is similar to the one of amorphous silicon systems (when comparing the temperature coefficients) and the degradation behavior seems to be closely related as well.

A summary of the discussed results can be found in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of systems degradation behaviors

Characteristic	Crystalline systems	Thin-film systems
Performance Ratio	Moderate decrease (0.4-1.1%/a)	Higher decrease (0.6-2.4%/a)
Current	Loss in power is primarily due to decrease in current	Power loss can be traced to both, loss in current and in voltage
Voltage	No visible decrease in voltage	
Affected electrical parameter	$I_{SC}, R_{sh}, FF,$	$I_{SC}, R_{sh}, FF, V_{OC}, R_s$
Degradation modes	Hot cells, damaged cells, metallization degradation	Metallization degradation, degradation of active material (assumptions)

4 SUMMARY & CONCLUSION

In this work, a study of the current and voltage behavior of different PV systems over time is performed. The results are linked to the performance ratio evolution, which is proportional to the evolution of the absolute power output over time. While considering different silicon and non-silicon based PV technologies, it became apparent that the technologies, which account for the majority of installed system on the market, polycrystalline and mono-crystalline silicon, experience the lowest performance loss over time. This observation is attributed to the maturity of this technology due to decades of research, development and field experiences but also to the stability of the crystalline base material. The study is conducted based on the examination of field data, whereby seven years of outdoor exposure are considered. Eight different technologies, divided into 27 different PV systems, are subject of the study. After pre-filtering the raw data, the current and voltage values are corrected, considering their dependency on temperature and irradiance, normalized using nominal data-sheet values and aggregated to receive monthly values. The trend lines of the time series data of I_{norm} , V_{norm} and PR are then extracted using STL. Finally, the trend lines are subject to the application of simple linear regression and the resulting monthly gradient is aggregated to compute the yearly performance loss.

It has been shown that the main driver for the decrease in PV power performance is a declining current output. The majority of systems under surveillance show this trend. Through the execution of EL, IR and visual inspections as well as IV curve recordings a decrease in current can be affiliated to damaged/partly disconnected cells, hot cells and circuitry discoloration. These prevailing degradation modes lower the shunt resistance and directly affect the operating current. The mentioned degradation modes were exclusively detected in crystalline systems.

The degradation of CIGS, and partly also a-Si, systems seem to be rooted from different causes. Three out of four CIGS systems show an unusual high performance loss rate in voltage. A decrease in voltage is often connected to an increasing series resistance. It is assumed that this is connected with a reduction in the conductivity of the metal

contacts or a decreasing ability of the photovoltaic active material to separate the charge carriers.

It became apparent that the connection of specific degradation modes to PV system performance is a difficult task. The detection of a single degradation mode formation within a PV system, instead of a single module, is complicated because of the relatively low impact on electrical parameter. Furthermore, the appearance of degradation modes in thin-film systems is more difficult to detect compared to crystalline systems. Yet, we are convinced that further studies to improve the detection time and quality will contribute to early detection methodologies. This will ultimately lead to the development of early-state counteract mechanisms within O&M routines.

For a qualitatively more profound study, measurements on module level are suggested. This type of studies would serve as an advancement of knowledge in degradation mode occurrence and severity.

To better track the changes within the systems in the future, periodical recordings of IV curves will be crucial. The IV curve evolution over time is providing essential information about the change in series and shunt resistances, which in turn are directly affecting the current and voltage behavior of the system in question. Furthermore, visual inspections, IR and EL imaging are viable tools for the connection of the IV curve evolution and occurring degradation modes. A more thorough study of performance degradation of PV installations and its root causes will enrich the common knowledge about the occurrence and severity of degradation modes and other technical risks in specific climates. This expertise will be viable for the improvement of O&M best practices and help to develop reliable insurance models. Apart from that, the accuracy of prediction scenarios of the performance of future PV systems can be improved based on these studies, which in turn will contribute to setting up stronger business cases for PV installations.

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